

Infrastructures' Catalogue

Marine Institute

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1. Executive Summary

AQUARIUS is a Horizon Europe funded project that runs from March 1, 2024, to the end of February 2028. Its overarching aim is to provide a highly comprehensive suite of integrated research infrastructures designed to address significant challenges for the long-term sustainability of our unique oceans, seas, and freshwater ecosystems. An impressive range of 57 research infrastructure services will be made available through Transnational Access (TA) Calls, including research vessels, mobile marine observation platforms, fixed marine facilities, experimental research facilities, river & basin supersites, aircraft, drones, satellite services, and sophisticated data infrastructures.

A bespoke catalogue was created to showcase these research infrastructures (RI), allowing call applicants to view the RI on offer in the project and make informed proposals for transnational access (TA). This document outlines the process and steps taken to create the Infrastructures Catalogue. The catalogue was officially launched on the 29th of August 2024 and is available at <https://aquarius-ri.eu/ri-catalogue/>.

Once published online, the catalogue was reviewed by infrastructure operators to confirm all the details provided, and over the course of the project the catalogue will be routinely updated to reflect any changes to infrastructure, i.e., upgrading/decommissioning of equipment, editing training or documentation requirements, or to upload additional photos or technical specification sheets.

Activity on the website will be monitored throughout the project, and the catalogue will be publicised extensively using press releases and social media to reach relevant audiences.

2. Introduction

D4.1 is related to Task 4.1 of the DoA, which is:

“Online Infrastructures’ Catalogue Created M1 -M48”

The catalogue will serve as the primary public communications platform for disseminating key scientific and technical information related to AQUARIUS Research Infrastructure. These RI 'profiles' would be presented in a user-friendly format on the AQUARIUS website, ready by the first Call launch on November 11th, 2024.

The overall aim for this task was to design and create profiles that would classify each AQUARIUS RI by type and location/area of operation (based on the 'Lighthouse Regions'), and provide scientific and technical information on the services provided, instrumentation available, variables measured, periods of availability, contact information for further inquiries by researchers, and outline any mandatory documentation or personnel certification associated with accessing and using an infrastructure. This information would be compiled and published in a comprehensive online catalogue available to call applicants interest in accessing AQUARIUS RI and profiles would be updated regularly to reflect any changes to a RI, i.e., new, or decommissioned equipment, availability periods, etc.

3. Method and Results

3.1. RI Profile Template Design

To develop the AQUARIUS Infrastructure Catalogue, firstly each of the Research Infrastructures were examined and classified into 8 RI types, that are:

- Research Vessels
- Marine Mobile Observation Platforms
- Fixed Marine Facilities
- Experimental Research Facilities
- River & Basin Supersites
- Aircraft
- Drones
- Satellite Services

To capture the relevant scientific and technical information for each RI type, bespoke profile templates were tailored to each type, and drafts of these templates were circulated among some RI operators to gather feedback. This feedback was instrumental in refining the templates to ensure they captured all necessary information that potential applicants might need.

AQUARIUS is themed on the concept of Mission lighthouses, where EU seas and major river basins are divided into four regions, each with a particular priority to be addressed:

- The Atlantic-Arctic and the Danube & Black Sea regions focus on *protecting and restoring aquatic ecosystems*.
- The Baltic & North Sea is focused on *making the blue economy carbon neutral and circular*.
- The Mediterranean Sea targets *preventing and eliminating pollution*.

As these priorities need to be addressed by applicants in the Transnational Access (TA) Call proposals, it was important to group each infrastructure based on which region or regions they could serve. To determine this, the profile templates included an initial question where operators specified the appropriate lighthouse regions their infrastructure could serve (Figure 1).

Please check the Lighthouse region or regions your infrastructure can serve: *

Atlantic/Arctic

Baltic and North Sea

Mediterranean Sea

Black Sea

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Figure 1 RI Profile question for capturing which Lighthouse region or regions a particular infrastructure can serve

The final iteration of each of the Research Infrastructure Profile Templates can be found in Appendices 5.2 of this deliverable.

3.2. Profile Data Collection

After integrating the feedback received from operators, the revised templates were transformed into MS Forms, which served as the primary tool for collecting standardized information from operators. This method was anticipated to enhance the response rate by providing a structured and user-friendly way to submit data.

To streamline the process and reduce the need for multiple outreach efforts, the decision was made to include the WP5 Training Questionnaire and the WP6 Data Questionnaire within these forms. This integration aimed to cover all necessary aspects without the need for repeated follow-ups.

Figure 2: MS Forms profile template for Marine Mobile Observation Platforms

Additionally, a SharePoint link was made available for operators to upload photographs and detailed technical specifications of their infrastructure. This feature facilitated the easy incorporation of visual and technical data into the project’s website, further enriching the resource pool for potential applicants.

Initially, response rates were slow but improved as the deadline approached. In addition to MS Forms, the profile templates were also provided in Word, as users without a Corporate Microsoft Account could not resume or edit their forms, so were given the option to submit the template in a Word document. This proved useful, especially since different individuals handled the three sections: RI Profile, Data Questionnaire, and Training Questionnaire. As results came in these were quality checked, and operators were prompted if more input was required to their respective profiles.

3.3. Data Collation and Review

Infrastructure operators submitted their respective RI profile, and after each were quality checked, cleaned, and standardized along with every other RI profile, this data was then input onto a SharePoint spreadsheet. Answers to WP5 Training Questionnaire and the WP6 Data Questionnaire were extracted and sent to the relevant work package leaders.

Operators were invited to review the online spreadsheet of profile information, to provide final confirmation of their details or/and to make any edits to the active document.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	Infrastructure Profile										
2	Name of Infrastructure:	Infrastructure Provider:	Please check the Lighthouse region or regions your infrastructure can serve:	Location/Home Port Coordinates (Latitude)	Location/Home Port Coordinates (Longitude)	Organisation & Address	Infrastructure Webpage	Link to Vessel / Infrastructure Schedules (if applicable)	Normal Area of Operation	Maximum Number of Days Available	
3	RV Celtic Explorer	Marine Institute (MI)	Atlantic/Arctic;Baltic and North Sea;	Galway, Ireland	53.2738	-9.05178	Rinville, Oranmore, Co. Galway, Ireland.	https://www.marinet.ie/	10 & on a case by case basis depending on annual operational plan.	20 days	
4	RV Svea	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)	Baltic and North Sea	Lysekil, Sweden	58.267	11.433	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Ship Management Unit, P.O. Box 7021, 750 07 Uppsala, Sweden	https://www.slu.se/en/collaborative-centres-and-projects/research-vessel-svea/	Bothnian Sea 62.0885° N, 19.4019° E	10 days	
5	RV Sanna	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (GINR)	Atlantic/Arctic;	Nuuk, Greenland	64.167	-51.733	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Kivioq 2, 3900 Nuuk, Greenland	https://natur.gl/facilities/skibe/?lang=en	West Greenland, mainly near coastal waters	15 days	
6	RV Wim Wolff	Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ)	Baltic and North Sea;	Texel, The Netherlands	52.959	4.787	NIOZ Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research, Landsdiep 4 1797 SZ, 't Horntje (Texel), The Netherlands	https://viewer.folioson.com/preview/w02PZC/g4/rv-wim-wolff/	Coastal Netherlands (within 20 nm); Wadden Sea; Zeeland, North Atlantic Ocean, North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, Baltic Sea	10 days	
7	RV Belgica	Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS)	Atlantic/Arctic;Baltic and North Sea;	Zeebrugge, Belgium	51.336	3.199	Institute of Natural Sciences - 3de en 23ste Linieregimentsplein, B-8400 Ostend, Belgium	https://odnature.naturalsciences.be/belgica/en/table/	North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, Baltic Sea	15 days	

Figure 3: Excel document to collate all research infrastructure profile information

3.4. Integration with Online Catalogue

The integration of RI profiles into the AQUARIUS website began by sharing the profile data spreadsheet with SSBE (Work Package 7 (Communications and Dissemination) lead and website developer). This allowed SSBE to extract and incorporate the information into the online catalogue. Initially, to test the online infrastructure catalogue's environment, SSBE uploaded a profile for one research vessel. This step helped assess the layout and formatting. Based on feedback from MI, a preliminary design was established. Following this, SSBE uploaded one profile for each of the other seven types of research infrastructure. After further feedback and adjustments, a final layout was agreed upon for all eight research infrastructure profiles.

RV Celtic Explorer

Infrastructure Profile	
Infrastructure Provider	Marine Institute (MI)
Location/Home Port	Galway, Ireland
Location/Home Port Coordinates (Latitude)	53.2738
Location/Home Port Coordinates (Longitude)	-9.05178
Organisation & Address	Rinville, Oranmore, Co. Galway, Ireland

Figure 4: RI Catalogue – Profile for the RV Celtic Explorer

Additionally, a layout was agreed on for the RI Catalogue homepage. The original AQUARIUS infographic was adapted, and a new interactive map was created which served as a clickable feature for filtering infrastructures based on which lighthouse region they could serve.

Figure 5: Interactive map used on the RI Catalogue to filter infrastructures based on the lighthouse regions they can serve

Figure 6: Homepage of the Research Infrastructure Catalogue.

MI conducted a final review of the content and layout for each profile on the website while the site was under password protection. In some cases, follow-ups were necessary to obtain additional information or clarify details from infrastructure operators. After making the required edits or corrections, the URL and password credentials were circulated to all infrastructure operators who were invited to review their respective profiles and provide feedback. Any feedback received was collected by MI and forwarded to the developers for

further action. The official publicised launch of the catalogue was scheduled for August 29th, 2024, in time for the first AQUARIUS Brokerage Event on September 10th during the ICES Annual Science Conference.

4. Summary

The AQUARIUS Research Infrastructure catalogue was designed and developed to allow call applicants to view and apply for transnational access to various RIs offered in the AQUARIUS project. Officially launched on August 29th, 2024, the catalogue is accessible at <https://aquarius-ri.eu/ri-catalogue/>. Following its online publication, infrastructure operators reviewed the catalogue to ensure accuracy and completeness. The catalogue will be continuously updated to reflect changes in infrastructure, such as upgrades or decommissioning, or to add additional photos or technical specifications. The RI catalogue will serve as a key communication tool for scientific and technical information related to AQUARIUS RIs. The website's activity will be monitored, and the catalogue will be regularly promoted through press releases and social media.

5. Appendices

5.1. Appendix 1 - List of Transnational Access (TA) Providers

Below is a list of the AQUARIUS TA providers, their infrastructure(s) and links to the online Infrastructures Catalogue.

Type	Infrastructure	Provider	Country
1) Research Vessel	RV Gaia Blu	CNR	IT
1) Research Vessel	RV Sarmiento de Gamboa	CSIC	ES
1) Research Vessel	RV Jákup Sverri	FMRI	DE
1) Research Vessel	RV Mare Nigrum	GeoEcoMar	RO
1) Research Vessel	RV Sanna	GINR	GL
1) Research Vessel	RV Aegaeo	HCMR	GR
1) Research Vessel	RV Thalassa	IFREMER	FR
1) Research Vessel	RV L'Europe	IFREMER	FR
1) Research Vessel	RV G. O. Sars	IMR	NO
1) Research Vessel	RV Arni Fridriksson	MFRI	IS
1) Research Vessel	RV Celtic Explorer	MI	IE
1) Research Vessel	RV Wim Wolff	NIOZ	NL
1) Research Vessel	RV Belgica	RBINS	BE
1) Research Vessel	RV Svea	SLU	SE
1) Research Vessel	RV Socib	SOCIB	ES
1) Research Vessel	RV Aranda	SYKE	FI
1) Research Vessel	RV Tubitak Marmara	TÜBİTAK Marmara	TR
1) Research Vessel	RV Simon Stevin	VLIZ	BE
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	Baltic Gliders	FMI	FI
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	Max Rover	HCMR	GR
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	HROVARIANE	IFREMER	FR
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	SmartBay Glider	MI	IE
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	NorSOOP	NIVA	NO
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	SOCIB Glider Facility	SOCIB	ES
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	Alg@line	SYKE	FI

2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	UL-IROV	UL	IE
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	UL_MRE-ROV	UL	IE
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	AUJ Barabas	VLIZ	BE
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	USV Adhemar	VLIZ	BE
2) Mobile Marine Obs Platform	Glider Yoko	VLIZ	BE
3) Fixed Marine Facility	W1M3A - Western Mediterranean Research Facility	CNR	IT
3) Fixed Marine Facility	SiCO - Sicily Channel Observatory	CNR	IT
3) Fixed Marine Facility	CoCM - Corsica Channel Mooring	CNR	IT
3) Fixed Marine Facility	Utö Marine and Atmospheric Research Station	FMI	FI
3) Fixed Marine Facility	POSEIDON	HCMR	GR
3) Fixed Marine Facility	Western Ionian Sea (WIS)	INGV	IT
3) Fixed Marine Facility	SmartBay Observatory	MI	IE
3) Fixed Marine Facility	SmartBay Buoy	MI	IE
3) Fixed Marine Facility	IMDBON	MI	IE
3) Fixed Marine Facility	South Adriatic Sea E2M3A EMSO Regional Facility	OGS	IT
3) Fixed Marine Facility	PLOCAN Test Site	PLOCAN	ES
4) Experimental Research Facility	ISC-Lab	CNR	IT
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBRC-ERIC (Grouped)	EMBCR	FR
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (IMEV)	EMBCR	FR
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (OOB)	EMBCR	FR
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (SBR)	EMBCR	FR
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (CCMAR)	EMBCR	PT
4) Experimental Research Facility	EMBCR (CIIMAR)	EMBCR	PT
4) Experimental Research Facility	Lehanagh Pool	MI	IE
4) Experimental Research Facility	MI RAS	MI	IE
4) Experimental Research Facility	MESO & CAL	SYKE	FI
5) River & Basin Supersite	EMSO-EUXINUS	GeoEcoMar	RO
5) River & Basin Supersite	Elbe Supersite	HEREON	DE
5) River & Basin Supersite	Burrishoole Catchment & Research Facility	MI	IE
5) River & Basin Supersite	DANUBIUS-RI	GeoEcoMar	RO
5) River & Basin Supersite	iCIEM Ebro Delta Supersite	UPC	BE

6) Aircraft	FLIS	CzechGlobe	CZ
6) Aircraft	AIRS	OGS	IT
6) Aircraft	CWIS-II (AVIRIS-4)	VITO	BE
7) Drone	UL Drone	UL	IE
7) Drone	MAPEO	VITO	BE
8) Satellite Service	Terrascope	VITO	BE

5.2. Appendix 2 - Research Infrastructure Profile Templates

5.2.1. Research Vessels Profile Template

Research Vessel Profile

Technical Details (Research Vessels)	
Laboratory Facilities (fixed and temporary)	
CTD/Plankton sampling	
Multi-Beam(s)/ Sub Bottom profiling	
Fisheries Echo Sounders/Sonar	
USBL	
Coring/Sampling Capabilities	
Winches	
Communications	
Special features	
Suitable for: (list the type of surveys)	
Scientific Limitations (i.e. geophysics, coring, fisheries, any other discipline that cannot be performed on board for whatever the reason)	
Vessel capability to support ROV deployment	
Support Offered to Users	
Additional Capabilities/Equipment	

2. Vessel availability by location and by year/time of year for: (Please indicate location in coordinates and attach shapefile of the expected operational areas for each year. If no shapefile available then please provide a minimum of a combination of two lat / long coordinates to create a rectangle covering the area)

Year	Locations	Availability by Month	Ports of operation in the period of availability
2025			
2026			
2027			

3. Wish to be directly contacted by applicants in the proposal preparation?

Yes. Applicants are welcomed to discuss the initial feasibility of their work while they prepare their application with the operator of **XXXXX at e-mail address: XXXXXX**

No. The AQUARIUS Evaluation Office will forward any logistic question to the infrastructure operator.

Research Vessel Profile

- 4.** Certification requirements: Please indicate the medical certification required for joining the vessel and the list of acceptable certificates.

- 5.** Are additional medical checks required? If yes, please describe.

- 6.** Survival training certification required for joining vessel.

List of acceptable equivalent certification:

- 7.** Additional certification required e.g. Ship security awareness/other:

- 8.** Diplomatic clearance or other permits required and any relevant information about the application process?

- 9.** Please indicate any additional clearances required for area or type of activity:

5.2.2. Marine Mobile Observations Platforms Template

Marine Mobile Observation Platforms Profile

ROVs, AUVs, Gliders & USVs

[INSERT INFRASTRUCTURE NAME]

As part of Task 4.1, a catalogue of all available infrastructures will be compiled and made available on the online call application portal and project website.

Infrastructure Operators are asked to complete the standardised infrastructure profile templates below. User requirements prior to using the infrastructure should also be highlighted such as certification or training required for embarking on a campaign or use of specific infrastructure types. This will assist researchers in selecting the most appropriate infrastructures for their requirements and in planning their research project.

The information gathered will be compiled and published in a user-friendly fashion on the online portal in time for the launch of the first Call.

Part 1: Lighthouse Region of Service

Please check the Lighthouse region or regions your infrastructure can serve:

- Atlantic/Arctic:
- Baltic and North Sea:
- Mediterranean Sea:
- Black Sea:

Part 2: Standardised Infrastructure Profiles

1. Infrastructure Profile	
Location	
Location Coordinates	Latitude: Longitude:
Organisation & Address	
Infrastructure Webpage	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Link to Infrastructure Schedules (if applicable)	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Normal Area of Operation	Please insert Coordinates of area/areas of operation here <u>and</u> describe in text. Please upload Shapefiles of area also if available to the relevant SharePoint folder.
Max No of Days available	

Marine Mobile Observation Platforms Profile

ROVs, AUVs, Gliders & USVs

Dimensions							
Depth Rating	Length	Width	Height (incl. draft for USV)	Weight in Air	Total System Weight	Payload	Endurance (AUV, Gliders, USV)

Technical Detail (Marine Mobile Observation Platforms)

General Information	
Vessel Requirements (if applicable)	
Thrusters	
Cameras	
Positioning (USBL, etc)	
Instruments / Scientific Payload	
Optional Items	
Manipulators	
TMS (tether management system) (ROV Only), LARS details (if applicable)	
Support Offered to Users	

Marine Mobile Observation Platforms Profile

ROVs, AUVs, Gliders & USVs

2. Vessel availability by location and by year/time of year for: (Please indicate location in coordinates and attach shapefile of the expected operational areas for each year. If no shapefile available then please provide a minimum of a combination of two lat / long coordinates to create a rectangle covering the area)

Year	Locations	Availability by Month
2025		
2026		
2027		

3. Wish to be directly contacted by applicants in the proposal preparation?

We advise that all operators include a contact who can address applicants' queries directly.

Yes. Applicants are welcomed to discuss the initial feasibility of their work while they prepare their application with the operator of **XXXXX at e-mail address: XXXXXX**

No. The AQUARIUS Evaluation Office will forward any logistic question to the infrastructure operator.

4. Please indicate any diplomatic clearances or permits required for area or type of activity:

5.2.3. Fixed Marine Facilities Profile Template

Fixed Marine Facilities Profile

[INSERT INFRASTRUCTURE NAME]

As part of Task 4.1, a catalogue of all available infrastructures will be compiled and made available on the online call application portal and project website.

Infrastructure Operators are asked to complete the standardised infrastructure profile templates below. User requirements prior to using the infrastructure should also be highlighted such as certification or training required for embarking on a campaign or use of specific infrastructure types. This will assist researchers in selecting the most appropriate infrastructures for their requirements and in planning their research project.

The information gathered will be compiled and published in a user-friendly fashion on the online portal in time for the launch of the first Call.

Part 1: Lighthouse Region of Service

Please check the Lighthouse region or regions your infrastructure can serve:

- Atlantic/Arctic:
- Baltic and North Sea:
- Mediterranean Sea:
- Black Sea:

Part 2: Standardised Infrastructure Profiles

1. INFRASTRUCTURE Profile	
Location	
Location Coordinates	Latitude: Longitude:
Organisation & Address	
Infrastructure Webpage	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Link to Infrastructure Schedules if applicable	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Normal Area of Operation	Please insert Coordinates of area/areas of operation here <u>and</u> describe in text. Please upload Shapefiles of area also if available to the relevant SharePoint folder.
Max No of Days Available	

Fixed Marine Facilities Profile

Infrastructure Overview				
Depth of Operation	Power Supply	Communication System(s)	Dimensions	Sensors Available, Scientific Payload etc.

2. Scientific and Technical Details (Fixed Marine Facilities) – please provide a narrative outlining the scientific and technical capabilities of the infrastructure.

Be sure to outline the parameters that can be measured, their descriptions and data accessibility.

Narrative:

3. Infrastructure availability year/time of year for:

Year	Availability by Month
2025	
2026	
2027	

4. Wish to be directly contacted by applicants in the proposal preparation?

Yes. Applicants are welcomed to discuss the initial feasibility of their work while they prepare their application with the operator of **XXXXX at e-mail address: XXXXXX**

No. The AQUARIUS Evaluation Office will forward any logistic question to the infrastructure operator.

Fixed Marine Facilities Profile

5. Please indicate any additional clearances or documentation required for an area or type of activity:

6. Support offered to users: Please provide details about the support provided to AQUARIUS users.

5.2.4. Experimental Research Facilities Profile Template

Experimental Research Facility Profile

[INSERT INFRASTRUCTURE NAME]

As part of Task 4.1, a catalogue of all available infrastructures will be compiled and made available on the online call application portal and project website.

Infrastructure Operators are asked to complete the standardised infrastructure profile templates below. User requirements prior to using the infrastructure should also be highlighted such as certification or training required for embarking on a campaign or use of specific infrastructure types. This will assist researchers in selecting the most appropriate infrastructures for their requirements and in planning their research project.

The information gathered will be compiled and published in a user-friendly fashion on the online portal in time for the launch of the first Call.

Part 1: Lighthouse Region of Service

Please check the Lighthouse region or regions your infrastructure can serve:

- Atlantic/Arctic:
- Baltic and North Sea:
- Mediterranean Sea:
- Black Sea:

Part 2: Standardised Infrastructure Profiles

1. INFRASTRUCTURE Profile	
Location	
Location Coordinates	Latitude: Longitude:
Organisation & Address	
Infrastructure Webpage	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Link to Infrastructure Schedules if applicable	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Max No of Days Available	

Experimental Research Facility Profile

General Information				
Equipment & service components available	Testing and Analyses facilitated	Size and Capacity/Volume and Throughput	Turnaround time for testing and analyses	Data Formats / Data Acquisition Systems

2. Scientific and Technical Details (Experimental Research Facility) – please provide a narrative outlining the scientific and technical capabilities of the infrastructure. Use this field to highlight any special features worth noting.

Narrative/Description of Infrastructure:

Special Features:

3. Infrastructure availability year/time of year for:

Year	Availability by Month
2025	
2026	
2027	

4. Wish to be directly contacted by applicants in the proposal preparation?

Yes. Applicants are welcomed to discuss the initial feasibility of their work while they prepare their application with the operator of **XXXXX at e-mail address: XXXXXX**

No. The AQUARIUS Evaluation Office will forward any logistic question to the infrastructure operator.

Experimental Research Facility Profile

- 5.** Are any permits/certificates required for operations? If yes, please provide relevant information about the application process:

- 6.** Please indicate any additional clearances or documentation required for an area or type of activity:

- 7.** Support offered to users: Please provide details about the support provided to AQUARIUS users.

5.2.5. River and Basin Supersites Profile Template

River & Basin Supersites Profile

[INFRASTRUCTURE NAME]

As part of Task 4.1, a catalogue of all available infrastructures will be compiled and made available on the online call application portal and project website.

Infrastructure Operators are asked to complete the standardised infrastructure profile templates below. User requirements prior to using the infrastructure should also be highlighted such as certification or training required for embarking on a campaign or use of specific infrastructure types. This will assist researchers in selecting the most appropriate infrastructures for their requirements and in planning their research project.

The information gathered will be compiled and published in a user-friendly fashion on the online portal in time for the launch of the first Call.

Part 1: Lighthouse Region of Service

Please check the Lighthouse region or regions your infrastructure can serve:

- Atlantic/Arctic:
- Baltic and North Sea:
- Mediterranean Sea:
- Black Sea:

Part 2: Standardised Infrastructure Profiles

1. INFRASTRUCTURE Profile	
Location	
Location Coordinates	Latitude: Longitude:
Organisation & Address	
Infrastructure Webpage	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Link to Infrastructure Schedules (if applicable)	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Normal Area of Operation	Please insert Coordinates of area/areas of operation here <u>and</u> describe in text. Please upload shapefiles of area also if available to the relevant Sharepoint folder.
Max No of Days Available	

River & Basin Supersites Profile

General Information					
Breakdown of Equipment Available	Services & Sensors Available	Depth of Operation	Power Supply	Dimensions & Weight	Data Acquisition and Communication Systems

2. Scientific and Technical Details (River & Basin Supersites) – please provide a narrative outlining the scientific and technical capabilities of the infrastructure. Use this field to also outline and special features worth noting.

Narrative:

Special Features

River & Basin Supersites Profile

3. Infrastructure availability year/time of year for:	
Year	Availability by Month
2025	
2026	
2027	

4. Wish to be directly contacted by applicants in the proposal preparation?

Yes. Applicants are welcomed to discuss the initial feasibility of their work while they prepare their application with the operator of **XXXXX at e-mail address: XXXXXX**

No. The AQUARIUS Evaluation Office will forward any logistic question to the infrastructure operator.

5. Please indicate any additional clearances/certification or documentation required for an area or type of activity:

6. Support offered to users: Please provide details about the support provided to AQUARIUS users.

5.2.6. Aircraft Profile Template

Aircraft Profile

[INSERT INFRASTRUCTURE NAME]

As part of Task 4.1, a catalogue of all available infrastructures will be compiled and made available on the online call application portal and project website.

Infrastructure Operators are asked to complete the standardised infrastructure profile templates below. User requirements prior to using the infrastructure should also be highlighted such as certification or training required for embarking on a campaign or use of specific infrastructure types. This will assist researchers in selecting the most appropriate infrastructures for their requirements and in planning their research project.

The information gathered will be compiled and published in a user-friendly fashion on the online portal in time for the launch of the first Call.

Part 1: Lighthouse Region of Service

Please check the Lighthouse region or regions your infrastructure can serve:

- Atlantic/Arctic:
- Baltic and North Sea:
- Mediterranean Sea:
- Black Sea:

Part 2: Standardised Infrastructure Profiles

1. Infrastructure Profile	
Base Location	
Base Location Coordinates	Latitude: Longitude
Organisation & Address	
Infrastructure Web site address	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project.
Link to Infrastructure Schedules if applicable	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project.
Normal Area of Operation	Please insert Coordinates of area/areas of operation here <u>and</u> describe in text. Please upload Shapefiles of area also if available to the relevant SharePoint folder.
Maximum number of Days available	

Aircraft Profile

General Information						
Range	Seats	Service Ceiling	Gross Weight	Cruise/Service Speed	Top Speed	Endurance

2. Technical Detail (Aircraft)	
General Information	
Positioning	
Scientific Payload	
Mapping Capabilities	
Cameras	
Additional Items	
Limitation (weather or otherwise)	
Support Offered to Users: Please provide details about the support provided to AQUARIUS users.	

3. Wish to be directly contacted by applicants in the proposal preparation?

- Yes. Applicants are welcomed to discuss the initial feasibility of their work while they prepare their application with the operator of **XXXXX at e-mail address: XXXXXX**
- No. The AQUARIUS Evaluation Office will forward any logistic question to the infrastructure operator.

4. Aircraft availability by location and by year/time of year for: (Please indicate location in coordinates and attach shapefile of the expected operational areas for each year. If no shapefile available then please provide a minimum of a combination of two lat / long coordinates to create a rectangle covering the area)

Year	Location of operation	Availability by Month
2025		
2026		
2027		

5. Any additional personnel certification required, e.g., safety, medical, other...

6. Please indicate any clearances/permits required for area or type of activity?

5.2.7. Drones Profile Template

[INSERT INFRASTRUCTURE NAME]

As part of Task 4.1, a catalogue of all available infrastructures will be compiled and made available on the online call application portal and project website.

Infrastructure Operators are asked to complete the standardised infrastructure profile templates below. User requirements prior to using the infrastructure should also be highlighted such as certification or training required for embarking on a campaign or use of specific infrastructure types. This will assist researchers in selecting the most appropriate infrastructures for their requirements and in planning their research project.

The information gathered will be compiled and published in a user-friendly fashion on the online portal in time for the launch of the first Call.

Part 1: Lighthouse Region of Service

Please check the Lighthouse region or regions your infrastructure can serve:

- Atlantic/Arctic:
- Baltic and North Sea:
- Mediterranean Sea:
- Black Sea:

Part 2: Standardised Infrastructure Profiles

1. INFRASTRUCTURE Profile	
Base Location	
Base Location Coordinates	Latitude: Longitude:
Organisation & Address	
Infrastructure Webpage	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Link to Infrastructure Schedules if applicable	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Normal Area of Operation	Please insert Coordinates of area/areas of operation here <u>and</u> describe in text. Please upload Shapefiles of area also if available to the relevant SharePoint folder.
Max No of Days Available	

Drone Profile

General Information						
Flight Time (with & without payload)	Transmission Range	Altitude	Dimensions	Weight & max take-off weight	Weather Limits	Surveying Instruments Available

2. Scientific and Technical Details (Drone) – please provide a narrative outlining the scientific and technical capabilities of the infrastructure. Use this field to also highlight the scientific limitations, and any special features worth noting.

General Narrative/Description:

Scientific Limitation:

Special Features:

3. Infrastructure availability by location and by year/time of year for: (Please indicate location in coordinates and attach shapefile of the expected operational areas for each year. If no shapefile available then please provide a minimum of a combination of two Lat/Long coordinates to create a rectangle covering the area)

Year	Location	Availability by Month
2025		
2026		
2027		

Drone Profile

4. Wish to be directly contacted by applicants in the proposal preparation?

Yes. Applicants are welcomed to discuss the initial feasibility of their work while they prepare their application with the operator of **XXXXX at e-mail address: XXXXXX**

No. The AQUARIUS Evaluation Office will forward any logistic question to the infrastructure operator.

5. Airspace Clearance Requirements: Are any clearances required prior to a flight taking place? If yes, please indicate any time scales associate with clearance submissions:

6. Diplomatic Clearance Requirements: Are any permits required? If yes, please provide relevant information about the application process:

7. Please indicate any additional clearances or documentations required for an area or type of activity:

8. Support offered to users: Please provide details about the support provided to AQUARIUS users.

5.2.8. Satellites Profile Template

[NAME OF INFRASTRUCTURE]

As part of Task 4.1, a catalogue of all available infrastructures will be compiled and made available on the online call application portal and project website.

Infrastructure Operators are asked to complete the standardised infrastructure profile templates below. User requirements prior to using the infrastructure should also be highlighted such as certification or training required for embarking on a campaign or use of specific infrastructure types. This will assist researchers in selecting the most appropriate infrastructures for their requirements and in planning their research project.

The information gathered will be compiled and published in a user-friendly fashion on the online portal in time for the launch of the first Call.

Part 1: Lighthouse Region of Service

Please check the Lighthouse region or regions your infrastructure can serve:

- Atlantic/Arctic:
- Baltic and North Sea:
- Mediterranean Sea:
- Black Sea:

Part 2: Standardised Infrastructure Profiles

1. INFRASTRUCTURE Profile	
Operational Base:	
Operational Base Location Coordinates:	Latitude: Longitude:
Organisation & Address:	
Infrastructure Webpage	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Link to Vessel /Infrastructure Schedules if applicable	Please ensure this link will not expire during the project
Area of Coverage	Please insert Coordinates of area/areas of operation here <u>and</u> describe in text. Please upload shapefiles/KML files of area to the relevant Sharepoint folder.
Max No of Days Available:	

Satellites Profile

General Information				
Coverage Width	Image Resolution	Sensors Available	Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document (ATBD)	Tiling Grid KML

2. Scientific and Technical Details (Satellites) – please provide a narrative outlining the scientific and technical capabilities of the infrastructure.

General Narrative/Description:

Scientific Limitation:

Special Features:

3. Infrastructure availability by location and by year/time of year for: (Please indicate location in coordinates and attach shapefile of the expected operational areas for each year. If no shapefile available then please provide a minimum of a combination of two Lat/Long coordinates to create a rectangle covering the area)

Year	Location	Availability by Month
2025		
2026		
2027		

4. Wish to be directly contacted by applicants in the proposal preparation?

Yes. Applicants are welcomed to discuss the initial feasibility of their work while they prepare their application with the operator.

No. The AQUARIUS Evaluation Office will forward any logistic question to the infrastructure operator.

Satellites Profile

- 5.** Are any permits required for operations? If yes, please provide relevant information about the application process:

- 6.** Please indicate any additional clearances or documentation required for an area or type of activity:

- 7.** Support offered to users: Please provide details about the support provided to AQUARIUS users.

5.2.9. Data Management Questionnaire

Part 2: Data Management in RIs

One aim of AQUARIUS is to ensure that all data collected through TA cases will become available for EMODnet and Copernicus Marine in a FAIR way and with CC-BY-4.0 license. For this purpose, WP6 is dedicated to Data Management and includes a team of National Oceanographic Data Centres and other Data Management experts that will interact with TA researcher teams and with RIs to give support for deploying proper marine data management in different stages of the TA cases, starting with Data Management Plans and follow through until metadata and data publishing in leading European marine data management infrastructures such as SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, EBI-ENA, that are feeding into EMODnet thematics.

The answers to this survey will give a better understanding to WP6 partners and the survey will be followed up by dialogues from WP6 to the RIs for a) clearing up possible remaining questions and b) discussing the interfacing between each RI as observing system and the NODCs. The outcomes will be instrumental towards briefing and training the TA research teams on the Data Management aspects.

Note: If this data has already been provided in EuroFleets, please enter 'NA' in the required fields.

As a starter WP6 is interested in the AQUARIUS RIs that will provide TA and in particular in their Data Management practices. For this purpose, we would like each AQUARIUS TA RI to provide input to the following questions.

Please provide a short overall description of the RI, highlighting what will be offered to TA users:

What kind of platforms? *

What kind of data types? *

What kind of instrumentation? *

How are data as collected via the RI managed?

Does it include direct in-situ data observations and/or samples?

In case of direct in-situ observations – Is there a Data Management facility? *

Yes

No

What metadata format(s)?

What data format(s)?

How is data access provided for TA users?

Is there already an exchange with any of the European MDM infrastructures (SeaDataNet, EuroBIS, EBI-ENA, ..)?

In case of samples – Does the RI provide processing facilities as part of TA, such as laboratories or dedicated software application? *

Yes

No

What metadata format(s)?

What data format(s)?

How is data access provided for TA users?

Is there already an exchange with any of the European MDM infrastructures (SeaDataNet, EuroOBIS, EBI-ENA,...)?

5.2.10. Training Questionnaire

Part 4 Training

Introduction:

The purpose of this section is to identify any training needs and gap analysis that can be addressed to ensure that the RI can be used appropriately and efficiently to maximise the benefit for the researchers and their projects. A database of all training access requirements will be produced in advance of the first Transnational Access call to inform users. All training resources will be shared via the *AQUARIUS Technical Training Hub* throughout the project.

Q 1. Are Infrastructure Users required to undertake any training prior to accessing your infrastructure?

- YES
- NO (Go to Q4)

If yes, please provide details

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Q 2. Do you (Infrastructure Operator) provide the training or is it provided by an external organization?

- Infrastructure Operator provides the training
- External Organization provides the training

Please provide details

--

Q 3. Do you organize the training for the Users or is it Users' responsibility to organize training?

- Infrastructure Operator organizes training
- Users organize training

Q 4. Is there training material available to ensure that the RI can be used appropriately and efficiently to maximise the benefit for the researchers and their projects?

- YES (go to Q5)
- NO (go to Q6)

Q 5. What kind of material is available online?

Webinar		
Workshop(s)		

Research Vessel Profile

Video		
Brochure		
Presentation (ppt, pdf)		
Other		

If you selected Other, please specify here.

Q 6. Do you plan to provide any online training materials before the 1st TA call (November 2024) / or before of end JUNE?

- YES
- NO

If Yes, please provide details (when will the training materials be available?)

Q 7. Are you willing to share available training material (if any) on the AQUARIUS Training Hub?

- YES
- NO

Q 7. Is on-site training necessary for TA users to utilize the RI?

- YES
- NO

Q 8. If requested by TA users, will you arrange on-site or on-line training course?

- YES
- NO

If no, please provide details